

EBFMC25-IP-03 · Home Health Care Services in Turkey: Current Situation, Challenges and Future Perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Home-based health care services have an essential role in the continuity of patient care, especially in patients with chronic diseases. The need for these services increases as elderly population increases, as patients living with chronic diseases also increase. Home-based health care services are provided by a multidisciplinary team consisting of physicians, nurses and other health professionals to support the disabled patients, elderly patients, chronically ill patients or patients in the process of recovery. The services are delivered in the places that they live to reduce the burden on both the patient and the caregiver. The teams provide patient and caregiver education as well as counselling services. Current regulations about home-based health care services have been defined recently and the scope of these services has expanded. Home-based health care services can utilize remote health services. Future developments can include digitalized home-based health care services and advanced remote patient monitoring. In conclusion, regulations and definitions of home-based health care services will be needed according to the needs, variability and risks that may arise from using advanced technological developments.

KEYWORDS

Health care, aging, chronic disease, elderly, remote patient monitoring

INTRODUCTION

Home-based health care services provide medical care, follow-up and rehabilitation services including social and psychological counselling and support services at home and in their home environment (Bahar & Beşer, 2017)

In Türkiye, the elderly population is increasing and the number of people living with chronic diseases is also increasing. The Turkish Statistical Institute (TUIK) reported that the elderly population (aged 65 years and over) in Turkey increased by 24% in the five years between 2016 and 2021, reaching 9.7% of the total population. In 2025, the elderly population is projected to be 11% of whole population (Türkiye İstatistik Kurumu [TÜİK], 2021)

Home-based health care services play a very important role in ensuring the continuity of patient care, especially in the follow-up of people with chronic diseases (Bahar & Beşer, 2017)

First home care services provided in the home environment are defined by regulations in 2005 by the Ministry of Health (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2005). Then regulations about the Home-Based Health Care Services defined the principles of service and procedures in implementation throughout the country. To support the physically and mentally disabled patients, elderly patients, chronically ill patients or patients in the process of recovery in their environments that they live in, to ensure that they can adapt to social life and continue their lives in a peaceful way, to reduce the burden of illness on both the patient and the caregiver home-based health care services are provided (Bahar & Beşer, 2017)

Since 2023 the new regulations have defined the home-based health care patient as an individual who is dependent on a device, bedbound or housebound due to diagnosed diseases, and/or has difficulty accessing health care services due to old age, who request home health care services at their place of residence, and whose request is deemed appropriate (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023)

All elderly aged 80 and over who request service, patients aged 65 and over who have a chronic disease documented by a medical board report and who are described as fully dependent or severely dependent in terms of activities of daily living score, patients who are device and/or home-bound due to their illness, patients who have received palliative care services and whose medical care is deemed appropriate to be provided at home are also defined as home-based health care patient population (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023) In the new regulation, the scope of home-based health care services were expanded; standards were determined. Patients who are deemed suitable for continuous medical care services for which a treatment plan is made when they are being discharged from the hospital and individuals who need medical care for up to thirty days after discharge from the health facility (which can be extended by the physician for up to thirty days if necessary) are also in the scope of the home-based health care services (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023) Diabetes, heart failure, stroke, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, Alzheimer's/dementia, neurodegenerative diseases, terminal cancer, chronic patients with multimorbidity, patients who are treated and followed up after hip/knee/shoulder fracture and patients who need medical care due to amputation are prioritised within the scope of home health care (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023)

"ESH-H" Home Health Service Units are established within secondary and tertiary health care facilities, and "ESH-D" is established in oral and dental health centres or oral and dental hospitals. "ESH-H" consists of one or more than one teams (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023) The team may consist of a physician or specialist physician, nurse, midwife, community health technician, health officer, home patient care technician, elderly care technician, psychologist, social worker, physiotherapist, pharmacist, dietician, driver and other professionals required by home based health care service (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023). "ESH-D" consists of a dentist, a health officer, an oral and dental health technician or dental prosthesis technician and a driver to provide oral and dental health services to patients provided during working hours (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023)

The procedures are carried out through the ESYS (Home Health Management System) software system. Healthy Aging Center staff work in accordance with home-based health care staff. The use of remote health services in home-based health care services has also been defined (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2022, 2023).

According to the needs of the patient's treatment plan, the physician in charge may include other health staff in the team and also multidisciplinary physicians can be assigned to the teams according to the medical needs of the patient. In addition, transport to and from the hospital can be planned by home health teams when necessary. Before the provision of home-based health care services consent of the patient and / or his/her parents, guardian, relatives of the patient is obtained and recorded (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023)

In units; teams can be planned to provide services in areas of medical needs such as palliative care, wound care, burn care, tracheostomy, clinical nutrition, physical therapy and rehabilitation, and rational drug use. The teams ask about both the medications and the herbal products used by the patients (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023).

In the provision of Home-Based Health Care Services, during patient visits, the patient's medical history, habits, current diseases, medications, compliance with treatment, active complaints related to health are asked to the patient or caregivers and recorded in the patient file (Bahar & Beşer, 2017). Physical examination, neurological examination of the patient is performed and recorded. Clinical frailty status and possible functional deficiencies are determined by evaluating the patient's activities of daily living such as eating, bathing, dressing, going to the toilet, getting out of bed and chair, urinary and faecal control and, and instrumental daily life activities such as using the telephone and taking medication on their own (Bahar & Beşer, 2017; T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023).

To determine the risk of falling, evaluations and necessary adjustments to organise the place where they live in a way to protect them from possible falls should be advised to the relatives or caregivers of elderly patients, especially those with chronic diseases (Bahar & Beşer, 2017; T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023). Oral and dental health are also important for patients receiving home health care. When necessary, patients should apply to an Oral and Dental Health Care teams (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023)

If physical examination findings of abuse and neglect are detected in the general assessment of the patient, this situation is recorded and necessary notifications are made to the relevant public institutions and organisations in accordance with the provisions of the relevant legislation (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023).

Within the scope of ESH, interventional medical services that can be performed at home in line with the patient's current condition and treatment plan are provided. Before these procedures are carried out, the patient

and/or his/her parents, guardian, relatives of the patient are informed and their consent is obtained and recorded (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023).

Patients should also be evaluated in terms of cognitive functions, nutritional status, possible dementia, depression and psychosocial risks. Patients may have problems such as decubitus ulcers. Patients at risk are also evaluated by the multidisciplinary team and necessary treatment and care processes are carried out (Bahar & Beşer, 2017; T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2023).

In addition, patients may have psychosocial problems and caregivers may have problems with disease awareness and care. Another important issue is that caregivers and relatives of the patient should be aware of the patient's disease, treatment, medications, and follow-up process and progression (Bahar & Beşer, 2017). Home-based health care teams provide patient and caregiver education and counselling services. For these reasons, the home health team should work multidisciplinary in line with the medical condition and needs of the patient when necessary (Bahar & Beşer, 2017). Although it varies according to the diagnosis and clinical condition of the patient, the caregivers should also have sufficient knowledge about the management of acute symptoms and the conditions in which the patient should apply to the emergency department (Bahar & Beşer, 2017)

Future perspectives can include digitalized home-based health care services, telemedicine and advanced remote patient monitoring. Mobile technologies such as wearable devices, sensors, smartphone applications can be utilized to enhance monitorization of the patient with chronic diseases (Serrano et al., 2023). Health care staff can use digital devices in monitoring and reaching out the patients and caregivers. Telehealth consultations can also be utilized by the patients and the physicians and multidisciplinary health teams. These developments also need the appropriate infrastructure and financial support (Serrano et al., 2023). Finally, regulations and definitions of home-based health care services will need to be revised according to the needs, utilization variability and possible risks that may arise from using advanced technological developments.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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